

Research Article

Effects of Transpiration and Exothermic Fluid on Mixed Convection Flow in a Vertical Channel

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Abstract

An investigation is performed to study the effect of transpiration and exothermic fluid on mixed convection flow in vertical porous plates. The differential equations governing the flow have been solved by using the Differential Transformation Method. Suction/injection is used to control the fluid flow in the channel. Numerical results are presented graphically and discussed quantitatively with respect to various parameters embedded in the problem. The results show that, the maximum flow of velocity, temperature and concentration are recorded, at the lower and upper plate by showing an increase in all parameters used. The present results are in good agreement with the previously published numerical results.

Key words: Transpiration, mixed convection, differential transformation method, exothermic chemical reaction, and vertical channel.

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Nomenclature

The different parameters that govern the flow in dimension form are as follows:

Pr =	Prandtl number
" =	Dimensionless Temperature
U =	Dimensionless Velocity of the fluid
y =	Dimensionless Co-ordinate perpendicular to the plate
x =	Dimensionless Co-ordinate parallel to the plate

N	=	Sustentation Parameter
K_r	=	Frank – Kamenetskii Parameter
$\}$	=	Mixed Convection parameter
x	=	Constant pressure gradient
x_c	=	Wall concentration
x_t	=	Wall temperature
S	=	Suction/Injection parameter
Sc	=	Schmid number

Introduction

The process of heat transfer by mixed convection flow over vertical surfaces occurs in many industrial and technical applications which include nuclear reactors cooled during emergency shutdown, electronic devices cooled by fans, solar central receivers, exposed to wind currents, and heat exchangers placed in a low velocity environment and so on. Several authors contributed in this area. Few of them are: Uwanta and Hamza (2014) studied the effect of suction/injection on the unsteady hydromagnetic convective flow of reactive viscous fluid between vertical porous plates with thermal diffusion. Flow of fully developed mixed convection in a vertical channel with chemical reaction has been analyzed by Saleh *et al.* (2013). Steady/Unsteady natural convection flow of reactive viscous fluid in a vertical annulus has been investigated by Ahmad and Jha (2013). Chamkha *et al.* (2011) discussed the effects of Joule heating, chemical reaction and thermal radiation on unsteady hydromagnetic natural convection boundary layer flow with heat and mass transfer of a micro polar fluid. Numerical investigation of buoyancy effects on hydro magnetic unsteady flow through a porous channel considering suction and injection has been studied by Makinde and Chinyoka (2013). Pop *et al.* (2009) investigated numerically by using the implicit finite difference scheme, the effect of heat generated by an exothermic reaction on the fully developed mixed convection flow in a vertical channel. Hamza (2016) discussed the influence of free convection slip flow of an exothermic fluid in a vertical channel. Chamka (2010) considered a coupled heat and mass transfer by the mixed convective flow of a non Newtonian power-law fluid over a permeable wedge embedded in a porous medium with variable surface temperature and concentration and heat generation or absorption and wall transpiration effects. Das and Jana (2010) analyzed heat and mass transfer effects on unsteady free convection flow near a moving vertical plate in porous medium. An investigation has been made by Al-Sanea (2004) on mixed convection heat transfer along a continuously moving heated vertical plate with suction or injection.

Makinde and Sibanda (2008) studied magneto hydro dynamic (MHD) mixed convection heat and mass transfer flow past a vertical porous plate embedded in a porous medium with constant heat flux. Habibis *et al.* (2013) discussed the criteria for the onset of flow reversal of the fully developed mixed convection in a vertical channel under the effect of the chemical reaction. Dileep and Vikas (2011) studied a thermal radiation effects on mixed convection flow and viscous heating in a vertical channel partially filled with a porous medium. Mixed convection flow of couple stress fluid in a vertical channel with radiation and Soret effects was reported by Kalandhar *et al.* (2016). Shojaefard *et al.* (2015) used suction/injection to control fluid flow on the surface of subsonic aircraft by controlling the flow as such, fuel consumption might be decreased by 30%, a considerable reduction in pollutant emission is achieved, and operating costs of commercial airplanes are reduced by atleast 8%. Attia (2002) discussed fully on unsteady flow due to a rotating disk with uniform suction or injection.

Unsteady free convection and mass transfer flow over an infinite vertical porous plate considering suction or injection has been reported by Takhar *et al.* (2003). Cortell (2011) studied the effects of suction, viscous dissipation, and thermal radiation on flow and heat transfer of a power-law fluid past an infinite porous plate.

The aim of the present analysis is to study the effect of suction/Injection and exothermic fluid on mixed convection flow in a vertical porous plate. In this paper an exothermic chemical reaction is employed and suction/injection is used to control the flow in the channel.

Mathematical Analysis

Consider a steady fully developed mixed convection flow of an exothermic fluid in a vertical channel. Choose the coordinate system such that x - axis be taken along vertically upward direction through the central line of the channel, y is perpendicular to the plates and the two plates are extended in the direction of x . The two walls separated by a distance L , i.e the channel width. A coordinate system is chosen such that the x -axis is parallel to the gravitational acceleration g , but with the opposite direction. The y -axis is orthogonal to the channel walls, and the origin of the axes is such that the position of the channel walls is $y = 0$ and $y = L$ respectively. A sketch of the system and of the coordinate axes is reported in the **Fig. 1**. We assume that in the channel the heat is supplied to the surrounding fluid by an exothermic surface reaction. The flow is subjected to the suction of the fluid from one porous plate and at the same rate fluid is being injected to other porous plate. The fluid velocity u is assumed to be parallel to the

x-axis. Following Pop *et al.* (2009), the governing equations in dimensional form can be written as

$$-\epsilon_0 \frac{du'}{dy'} = \epsilon \frac{d^2u'}{dy'^2} + gS (T' - T'_0) + gS^* (C' - C'_0) - \frac{1}{\dots} \frac{dP'}{dx'} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$-\epsilon_0 \frac{dT'}{dy'} = r \frac{d^2T'}{dy'^2} + QK_0 a e^{-E/RT'} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$-\epsilon_0 \frac{dC'}{dy'} = D \frac{d^2C'}{dy'^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Subject to the boundary condition

$$\begin{aligned} u = 0, \quad T = T'_1, \quad C = C'_1, \quad y' = 0 \\ u = 0, \quad T = T'_2, \quad C = C'_2, \quad y' = L \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1 Schematic Diagram of the Problem

We introduce the following non dimensional quantities

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x = \frac{x'}{\text{Re}L}, \quad y = \frac{y'}{L}, \quad u = \frac{u'}{u_0}, \quad p = \frac{p'}{\dots u_0^2} \\ \theta = \frac{T - T'_0}{RT_0^2/E}, \quad W = \frac{C - C'_0}{RC'_0/E}, \quad \text{Re} = \frac{u_0L}{\epsilon} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (5) in to (1) to (3) we have the following differential equations

$$\frac{d^2 u}{dy^2} + S \frac{du}{dy} + \left\{ \chi_t + N \chi_c \right\} u = \chi \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d^2 \theta}{dy^2} + S Pr \frac{d\theta}{dy} + K_r e^{(\cdot)} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d^2 W}{dy^2} + S Sc \frac{dW}{dy} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Subject to the following boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} u = 0, \quad \theta = \chi_t, \quad W = \chi_c \quad \text{at } y = 0 \\ u = 0, \quad \theta = -\chi_t, \quad W = -\chi_c \quad \text{at } y = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where $S, S_c, Pr, \chi_t, N, \chi, K_r, \chi_t, \chi_c$ are suction/Injection, Schmidt number, Prandtl number, mixed convection parameter, sustantation parameter, pressure term, Frank-kamenetskii parameter, symmetric wall temperature and concentration respectively, which are defined as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \chi &= \frac{Gr}{Re}, & \chi &= \frac{dp'}{dx'}, & \chi_t &= \frac{T_1' - T_0}{RT_0^2/E}, \\ \chi_c &= \frac{C_1' - C_0'}{RC_0^2/E}, & & & K &= \frac{EQK_0 aL^2}{RT_0^2 \Gamma} e^{-E/RT_0} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Method of Solution

Equations (6) to (8) subject to (9) are solved using D.T.M, the expressions of velocity, temperature and concentration respectively are displayed below.

$$U = Dy + \frac{[x + SD - \chi_t + N\chi_c]}{2} y^2 + \frac{[S^2 D + F_5]}{6} y^3 + \frac{[F_6 + S^3 D]}{24} y^4 + \frac{[F_7 + S^4 D]}{120} y^5 + \dots \quad (11)$$

$$\theta = \chi_t + B y + \frac{D_1}{2} y^2 + \frac{D_2}{6} y^3 + \frac{D_3}{24} y^4 + \frac{D_4}{120} y^5 + \dots \quad (12)$$

$$W = A y + \frac{S S_c A}{2} y^2 + \frac{S^2 S_c^2 A}{6} y^3 + \frac{S^3 S_c^3 A}{24} y^4 + \frac{S^4 S_c^4 A}{120} y^5 + \dots \quad (13)$$

The expression of skin friction, at the plate $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ are displayed respectively.

$$\frac{du}{dy} \Big|_{y=1} = D + [X + SD - \dots] (X_t + NX_c) + \frac{[S^2D + F_5]}{2} + \frac{[F_6 + S^3D + \dots]}{6} + \frac{[F_7 + S^4D + \dots]}{24} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{du}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} = D \quad (15)$$

The rate of heat transfer at the plate $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ respectively are:

$$\frac{d_n}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} = B \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d_n}{dy} \Big|_{y=1} = B + H_1 + \frac{H_2}{2} + \frac{H_3}{6} + \frac{H_4}{24} + \dots \quad (17)$$

The rate of mass transfer at the plate $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ respectively are:

$$\frac{dW}{dy} \Big|_{y=0} = A \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{dW}{dy} \Big|_{y=1} = A + SS_c A + \frac{S^2 S_c^2 A}{2} + \frac{S^3 S_c^3 A}{6} + \frac{S^4 S_c^4 A}{24} \quad (19)$$

Where A, B, D, H, F and some basic terms in differential transformation method (DTM) are defined in the appendix

Results and Discussion

The results obtained are displayed graphically for velocity, temperature, concentration, skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number. Figure 2 illustrated the effect of wall temperature (χ_t) on the temperature profile. It is observed that the temperature of the fluid suppresses by increasing values of (χ_t) in case of suction/injection. It is evident from this figure that the temperature of the fluid flow is greater in case of injection than suction. Figure 3 shows the effect of Frank Kamenetskii (Kr) parameter and suction/injection parameter (S) on temperature profile which revealed that increasing (Kr) accelerates the temperature of the fluid flow in case of injection than suction. In figure 4 we have presented the response of wall concentration, which revealed that increasing values of (χ_c) accelerates the fluid flow in the presence of suction and injection. It is seen that the concentration of the fluid is greater in the case of injection than suction. Figure 5 demonstrated the influence of wall temperature on velocity distribution which exhibits that, increasing values of (χ_t) lead to a significant increase in the velocity of the fluid flow in the case of suction and injection. Figure 6

shows the effects of Frank Kamenetskii parameter on velocity profile. It is physically observed that the fluid flow increases with increasing values of Frank Kamenetskii parameter. It is also noticed from this figure that the velocity is faster in case of injection than suction. Figure 7 depicts the effect of mixed convection parameter (β) on velocity profile. It is noticed from this figure that, as the values of mixed convection parameter increases, the velocity of the fluid flow is enhanced in the case of suction and injection. Figure 8 reveals the effect of the sustentation parameter (N) on the velocity distribution. From figure 8, it is observed that increasing values of (N) leads to an improved fluid motion in the case of injection than suction. Figures 9(a) and 9(b) illustrated the effects of skin-friction against Fran-Kamenetskii parameter (Kr) at $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ respectively. It is observed that, the skin friction increases with increasing values of wall temperature (x_w). It is evident from figure 9(a) the fluid flow is faster and thicker than fluid flow in 9(b). Figures 10(a) and 10(b) show the effects of skin-friction against Fran-Kamenetskii parameter (Kr) with different values of (x_c), at $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ respectively. It is observed that, the skin friction increases with increasing values of wall concentration (x_c). It is noticed from figure 10(a) that the fluid flow is more enhanced than fluid flow in 10(b).

Fig 2: Comparison between the work of Pop *et al.* (2009) and the present work when $N = x_c = 0$, $\beta = 100$, $K = 1.5$

Fig 3: Temperature profiles for $\lambda = 100, K_r = 1.5$ with different values of χ_t

Fig 4: Temperature profiles for $\lambda = 100, \chi_t = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2$ with different values of K_r

Fig 5: Concentration profile for $\lambda = 100, K_r = 1.5, \chi_t = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2$ with different values of Sherwood number.

Fig 6: Velocity profile for $\beta = 100$, $K_r = 1.5$, with different values of χ_t

Fig 7: Velocity profile for $\beta = 100$, with different values of K_r

Fig 8: Velocity profile for $K_r = 1.5, \chi_t = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2$ with different values of λ

Fig 9: Velocity profile for $\beta = 100$, $K_r = 1.5$, $\chi_t = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 2$ with different values of N

Fig. 10: Variation of skin friction with different values of χ_t

Fig. 11: Variation of skin friction with different values of Sherwood number χ_c
 (a) (b)

Conclusion

In the present study, the effect of transpiration and exothermic fluid on mixed convection flow in a vertical channel is investigated. Differential Transformation Method is used to get the expression of velocity, temperature, concentration, Nusselt number, Sherwood number and skin-friction. Graphical results for the velocity, temperature, concentration, skin-friction rate of heat and mass transfer. Are presented and discussed with the various physical parametric values. It was found that in this present research work that there is an excellent agreement with Pop *et al.* (2009). From the research work conducted, it is concluded that:

- i. The temperature increases with the increase of K_r and χ_t
- ii. The concentration increases with the increase of χ_c
- iii. The velocity increases with the increase of χ_t , K_r and }
 }
 }
 }
- iv. The effect of Frank-Kamenetskii K_r and χ_c is to increase the skin-friction

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Appendix

$$D = G(1)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{SP_r - K_r}{2}$$

$$F_3 = \frac{S^2P_r^2B - SP_rK_r - K_r}{6}$$

$$F_5 = [x + Sx - \} S(x_t + Nx_c) - \} (B + Nx A)]$$

$$F_6 = [2x + SF_5 - 2\} (F(2) + NM(2))]$$

$$F_7 = [6x + SF_6 - 6\} (F(3) + NM(3))]$$

$$M(2) = \frac{SS_c A}{2}$$

$$M(3) = \frac{S^2S_c^2 A}{3}$$

$$B = \frac{f_1 + f_2 + f_3 - 2x_t}{f_4}$$

$$f_1 = \frac{K_r}{2} + \frac{K_r}{6} + \frac{K_r}{24} + \frac{K_r}{120}$$

$$f_2 = \frac{SP_rK_r}{6} + \frac{SP_rK_r}{24} + \frac{SP_rK_r}{120}$$

$$f_3 = \frac{S^2P_r^2K_r}{24} + \frac{S^2P_r^2K_r}{120} + \frac{S^3P_r^3K_r}{120}$$

$$f_4 = 1 + \frac{SP_r}{2} + \frac{S^2P_r^2}{6} + \frac{S^3P_r^3K_r}{24} + \frac{S^4P_r^4}{120}$$

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$$H_1 = SP_r B - K_r$$

$$H_2 = S^2 P_r^2 B - SP_r K_r - K_r$$

$$H_3 = S^3 P_r^3 B - S^2 P_r^2 K_r - SP_r K_r - K_r$$

$$H_4 = S^4 P_r^4 B - S^3 P_r^3 K_r - S^2 P_r^2 K_r - SP_r K_r - K_r$$

$$f_{12} = \frac{SS_c}{2} + \frac{S^2 S_c^2}{6} + \frac{S^3 S_c^3}{24} + \frac{S^4 S_c^4}{120}$$

$$A = \frac{-2\chi_c}{f_{12}}$$

1. If $y = e^{rx}$ then $Y(k) = \frac{\Gamma x}{k!}$ where r is a constant.
2. If $y = \frac{d}{dy}[f_*(x)]$ then $Y(k) = (k+1)F(k+1)$
3. If $y = \frac{d^2}{dy^2}[f_*(x)]$ then $Y(k) = (k+1)(k+2)F(k+2)$
4. If $y = \frac{d^n}{dy^n}[f_*(x)]$ then $Y(k) = \frac{(k+n)!}{k!} F(k+n)$